

Research Article

Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template

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Abstract: *The Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template is an innovative template using Microsoft words that helps students in preparing all components of the formal report based on a step-by-step approach with examples for each report section. Most students experience problems when it comes to organizing, drafting and formatting their reports resulting in either a half-baked or poorly done piece of work. This innovation addresses the said problems by integrating a pre-formatted template into Microsoft Word and offering a very simple straightforward approach to writing a report. The Report Crafr offers clear explanations for each relevant section of the report such as the title, the executive summary, the introduction, the method, the findings and discussions, the conclusions, recommendations, references and appendices. The template is designed specifically for the area of business and academics. This template ensures that every report is professionally structured and formatted which would help students to deliver high-quality work efficiently. The Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template is beneficial due to its wide acceptability among undergraduates and therefore offers an implementation-oriented approach to the problem of writing formal reports.*

Keywords: Formal Report; Business Communication; Report Template; Easy; Undergraduate students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the skills required of university students is the ability to write a formal business report. Report writing is a critical skill that university students need to master to succeed in their future careers and in their academic pursuits (Gámez & Cueallar, 2019). An effective report writing will benefit the students in their future professional careers. Report writing skills are taught to second-semester Business students and fourth semester accounting students in the subject of Business communication at UiTM Sabah. The course requirements include completing a range of written assignments with report writing being one of the key assessments. Although students have been exposed to writing reports, many struggle in producing high-quality work (Palpanadan, Ridzuan, Anuar, Zuraidi, & Abd Samat, 2021). These challenges arise from various factors, including the inability to understand the format guideline prescribed by the course assessment. Poorly written reports can result in lower grades, which also can impact their overall grades. Furthermore, students may not acquire the skills required of the course assessments. As a result, they may lack the necessary communication skills when they enter the workforce, particularly in professional environments where well-structured and clear reporting plays a vital role in decision-making, teamwork and managing projects.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many undergraduate business and accounting students struggle with organizing and writing formal business reports, leading to issues with structure, clarity, and cohesion. This challenge often results from a lack of understanding of the purpose and expectations of each report section. Additionally, the challenge also lies in their difficulties in presenting findings in a coherent manner. As a result, students tend to rely heavily on external and unverified source, and eventually risking plagiarism. Likewise, they face difficulties in submitting well-organized and professional-looking documents.

In the Business Communication course, students were encouraged to practice consistent writing. Based on the instructor's observation, majority of students struggle to begin their report writing because they are unsure on how to start and approach each section of the report which eventually leads to hesitation and confusion. Furthermore, some students struggle to understand the format guidelines and may not fully understand the requirements of the report. This further complicates their ability to start the writing process. As a result, they make slow progress in the initial stages of writing, which eventually affects the overall quality of their work. Therefore, to minimize these consequences, a comprehensive and innovative solution is needed. The "Reportcrafr: Easy Analytical Report Template" is designed to simplify the process of writing formal reports for undergraduate students to assist them in their writing journey.

3. REPORT CRAFTR: EASY ANALYTICAL REPORT TEMPLATE

Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template falls under the teaching and learning innovation. It is designed within a comprehensive and structured framework that supports undergraduate business and accounting students enrolled in the Business Communication course to assist them in the initial stages of writing. It is designed as a pre-formatted report template on Microsoft words and includes all the relevant sections of a formal report, providing students with a clear guide to follow. Each section of the report includes detailed explanations and relevant examples, from the cover page to appendices, making it easy for students to understand and improve their writing. Students are guided on how to use the template by the instructor in class. This template was provided to students in past and current semesters, resulting in faster writing progress and improved report quality. It has proven to be effective in streamlining the writing process.

4. OBJECTIVES

The objective of introducing the Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template, is to tackle the struggles faced by business and accounting students enrolled in Business Communication course in starting to write a formal business report. Additionally, the Report Crafr is introduced to motivate them to begin their writing without feeling pressured. Therefore, the research objectives are as follows:

- i. To provide students with a structured, user-friendly template for writing formal business reports.
- ii. To ensure students understand the purpose and content of each report section through embedded instructions.
- iii. To enhance students' ability to organize their thoughts and present information professionally.

- iv. To reduce the time students spend on formatting and organizing reports, allowing more focus on content quality.

5. NOVELTY

The Report Crafr is described as a structured and comprehensive guide designed specifically for undergraduate business and accounting students who are enrolled in Business Communication course. The innovation lies in combining a ready-made, editable template with a step-by-step guidance on report structure which makes it both functional and educational. Unlike templates that are pre-installed in Words, Report Crafr offers more detailed explanations within each section to explain its purpose and how to complete it. The Report Crafr is an integrated learning tool that offers the unique dual function of providing both content structure and educational guidance.

6. BENEFITS TO SOCIETY

The Report Crafr is a useful tool to prepare students for professional business environments by improving their report-writing skills, enhancing their ability to communicate complex ideas clearly and professionally, fostering better understanding and application of business communication principles, and contributes to producing independent, marketable graduates who are capable to produce high-quality work in real-world settings.

Firstly, this template equips students with the necessary skills in report writing that is relevant in the business environments. Students will be able to communicate complex ideas more effectively if they are highly proficient writing a good report. The ability to structure information in a professional way ensures that students are well-prepared to meet industry standards.

Secondly, the template encourages students to understand key concepts rather than relying on instructions, through a better understanding and application of business communication principles. A better understanding of business writing standards allows students to be more independent in learning to present and analyse information.

Furthermore, by enhancing these skills, the template ensures that students are capable of producing high-quality work in real-world professional settings. This includes the ability to write reports that are clear, well-organized and aligned with business environment standards. In addition, to contributing to better decision making within organizations, the practical application of the template would help enhance students' employability where employers seek graduates who can produce well-structured and insightful reports.

7. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL

The Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template can be commercialised as a standalone educational tool for online learning platforms or as part of digital learning packages for universities. IT can also be adapted for various business fields, such as, marketing, management and entrepreneurship courses. Potential exists for collaboration with educational publishers to make it part of a business communication module or learning suite.

8. CONCLUSION

The Report Crafr: Easy Analytical Report Template provides a practical, instructional tools which enhances both the students' report writing quality and learning outcomes. The template offers solution to address the common struggles faced by Business Communication students. There is a potential to adopt and customized the template on a wide scale basis. As an educational tool, it provides an innovative solution that enhances learning, support student development, and contributes to creating more effective and competent future professionals.

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